

Curvilinear Regression Models for Benzenoid Hydrocarbons

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Abstract

Chemical graph theory enables the use of several methods with important applications in drug design and development. The Van topological indices have been defined recently, which are based on neighbour vertex degree. This article examines the chemical application of the Van topological indices through regression models employing 22 benzenoid hydrocarbons. The chemical applicability of the Van topological indices is investigated in this study, using curvilinear regression models to analyze its relationship with the physico-chemical properties of benzenoid hydrocarbons. The statistical analysis data indicates that the Van topological indices have the potential to serve as a predictive index for the attribute of boiling point (BO), π -electron energy (π -ele), molecular weight (MW), polarizability (PO), molar volume (MV), and molar refractivity (MF).

Keywords: Topological descriptors, Van indices, benzenoid hydrocarbons, physicochemical properties, regression models.

1. Introduction

Topological indices can be used to quantify the structure of a molecule. These indices are calculated based on the molecular structure and have been widely used in the fields of chemistry and pharmacy. Indices play a crucial role in QSPR/QSAR analysis, which stands for Quantitative Structure Property/Activity Relationship. The data acquired from these indices differs depending on the algorithm selected. An effective method involves encoding the structural information of a molecule using molecular descriptors [1–4]. Topological indices utilize cost-effective and easy computing approaches, with a wide variety of indices currently available.

Only a small number of these indexes are widely used since they are application-based and are therefore extensively researched by several scholars globally. The indices can be verified as possibly predictive based on mathematical features and the compound's chemical application,

increasing the index's popularity [5–9]. Topological indices are also known as graph invariants as they are numerical values derived from the molecular graphs. These invariants are mostly utilized in drug discovery and development. As previously said, there is a vast number of topological indexes that continue to grow. Several variations of the current indices exist with adjustments implemented. The revised indices have been applied in chemical problem-solving.

Graphs play a crucial role in various chemistry disciplines for modeling chemical compounds based on molecular structure. The compounds' physicochemical properties are analyzed in respect to molecular descriptors in structure-property interactions. Graphs are widely used in various disciplines where graph theory skills are essential[10]. Molecular descriptors are tools defined based on specified rules.

The molecular descriptors can be categorized as degree-based, distance-based, and neighborhood degree-based[11–13]. Topological descriptors analyze the structure of a chemical substance to extract information about it. There are several descriptors, but only a select number are widely recognized due to their extensive usage.

Condensed polycyclic unsaturated conjugated hydrocarbons are also known as Benzenoid hydrocarbons. Six-membered rings composed of carbon and hydrogen atoms. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) have a different structure compared to benzenoid hydrocarbons. PAHs can have non-six-membered rings, often 5-membered carbon atom rings, but benzenoid hydrocarbons exhibit a dispersion of π -electrons with double bonds between specific pairs of carbon atoms [14–17].

PAHs offer a significant level of stability in terms of thermodynamic and chemical characteristics. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are chemical compounds composed of several aromatic rings. Naphthalene is composed of two aromatic rings, while anthracene and phenanthrene are aromatic compounds with three rings. Aromatic compounds are mostly present in oil and coal reserves, and are generally created by engines, incinerators, or the burning of biomass in forest fires. PAHs, as previously mentioned, can have rings of varying sizes, and some may not be fragrant. Alternants are chemicals that have six-membered rings.

PAHs exhibit σ bonds due to the fusion of sp^2 hybrid orbitals of neighboring carbon atoms in the same plane. Most PAHs are planar due to this reason [18–19]. PAHs can occasionally exhibit non-

planarity, caused by the length and angle of the rigidity, as well as the topology of the $C - C$ bonds inside the molecules.

Hydrocarbons are compounds composed of carbon and hydrogen atoms. They can exist in various forms such as planar, non-planar, alternant, and non-alternant aromatic hydrocarbons, alkyl- and alkenyl-substituted benzene derivatives, acyclic and polycyclic alkanes, strained and unstrained olefins, and complex structures incorporating aromatics like benzene and naphthalene.

This article uses common graph terminologies and notations from references [20–22].

This research focuses solely on assessing the effectiveness of Van molecular topological indices in predicting the chemical properties of BHs.

In Figure 1, images symbolizing the chemical structure of the benzenoid hydrocarbons (BHs) whose properties we examined are given.

Figure 1: (a) Benzene, (b) Naphthalene, (c) Phenanthrene, (d) Anthracene, (e) Chrysene, (f) Benzo[a]anthracene, (g) Triphenylene, (h) Tetracene, (i) Benzo[a]pyrene, (j) Benzo[e]pyrene, (k) Perylene, (l) Anthanthrene, (m) Benzo[ghi]perylene, (n) Dibenz[a,c]anthracene, (o) Dibenz[a,h]anthracene, (p) Dibenz[a,j]anthracene, (q) Picene, (r) Coronene, (s) Dibenzo[a,h]pyrene, (t) Dibenzo[a,i]pyrene, (u) Dibenzo[a,l]pyrene, (v) Pyrene [23].

The Van degree [24] of a vertex v of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$van(v) = \frac{\sum_{u \in N(v)} deg(u)}{\prod_{u \in N(v)} deg(u)} = \frac{S_v}{M_v}.$$

The inverse Van degree [24] of a vertex v of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$ivan(v) = \frac{\prod_{u \in N(v)} deg(u)}{\sum_{u \in N(v)} deg(u)} = \frac{S_v}{M_v}.$$

The first Van index [24] of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} van(v)^2.$$

The second Van index [24] of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v).$$

The third Van index [24] of a simple connected graph G defined as;

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

$$Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [van(u) + van(v)].$$

The first inverse Van index [24] of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^{1i}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} ivan(v)^2.$$

The second inverse Van index [24] of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^{2i}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} ivan(u)ivan(v).$$

The third inverse Van index [24] of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^{3i}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [ivan(u) + ivan(v)].$$

1. Main Results

This section examines how Van indices can be used to construct linear, quadratic, and cubic regression models for various properties of benzenoid hydrocarbons, such as boiling point (BO), π -electron energy (π -ele), molecular weight (MW), polarizability (PO), molar volume (MV), and molar refractivity (MF). Table 1 shows the physical characteristics of benzenoid hydrocarbons, as well as their calculated Van indices.

Table 1. Physical characteristics and estimated Van indices

Derivatives of Benzene	BP	π -ele	MW	PO	MV	MR	Van^1	Van^2	Van^3	Van^{1i}	Van^{2i}	Van^{3i}
a-Benzene	78,8	8	78,11	10,4	89,4	26,3	6	6	12	6	6	12
b-Naphthalene	221,5	13,683	128,17	17,5	123,5	44,1	7,4583	7,6181	18,1667	15,6376	17,9673	27,8857
c-Phenanthrene	337,4	19,448	178,23	24,6	157,7	61,9	9,2423	9,429	24,1667	28,6426	34,6454	46,1557
d-Anthracene	337,4	19,314	178,23	24,6	157,7	61,9	9,0278	9,5139	24,3333	26,0151	31,1918	44,1714
e-Chrysene	448	25,192	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	11,0262	11,2593	30,1667	41,6476	51,6104	64,4857
f-Benzo[a] anthracene	436,7	25,101	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	10,8117	11,348	30,3333	39,0201	48,0306	62,4714
g-Triphenylene	425	25,275	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	11,3519	11,4074	30	45,015	56,775	66,9
h-Tetracene	436,7	25,188	228,3	31,6	191,8	79,8	10,5972	11,4097	30,5	36,3927	44,4163	60,4571
i-Benzo[a]pyrene	495	28,222	252,3	35,8	196,1	90,3	10,9784	11,4568	32,3333	56,6501	71,6639	80,2714
j-Benzo[e]pyrene	467,5	28,336	252,3	35,8	196,1	90,3	10,7276	10,8495	31,3333	120	79,8989	84,8857
k-Perylene	467,5	28,245	252,3	35,8	196,1	90,3	11,2485	12,4691	32,1667	120	77,0393	82,4857
l-Anthanthrene	497,1	31,253	276,3	40	200,4	100,8	11,2361	11,9306	34,8333	138	91,7371	95,6571
m-Benzo[ghi] perylene	501	31,425	276,3	40	200,4	100,8	11,1415	11,6512	34,3333	138	97,1111	98,0714
n-Dibenz[a,c] anthracene	518	30,942	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	12,9213	13,3495	36,1667	128	70,3209	83,1857
o-Dibenz[a,h]anthracene	524,7	30,881	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	12,5957	13,1821	36,3333	128	64,8693	80,7714
p-Dibenz[a,j]anthracene	524,7	30,88	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	12,5957	13,1821	36,3333	128	64,8693	80,7714
q-Picene	519	30,943	278,3	38,7	225,9	97,6	12,8102	13,0895	36,1667	128	68,5754	82,7857
r-Coronene	525,6	34,572	300,4	44,1	204,7	111,4	11,0417	11,8333	36,5	156	118,1829	113,6571
s-Dibenzo[a,h] pyrene	552,3	33,928	302,4	42,9	230,2	108,1	12,8179	13,4136	38,3333	146	89,6193	98,7714
t-Dibenzo[a,i] pyrene	552,3	33,954	302,4	42,9	230,2	108,1	12,8179	13,4136	38,3333	146	89,6193	98,7714
u-Dibenzo[a,l] pyrene	552,3	34,031	302,4	42,9	230,2	108,1	13,1443	13,608	38,25	146	97,3293	101,6286
v-Pyrene	404	22,506	202,25	28,7	162	72,5	9,7222	10,25	27,8333	94	42,1371	56,3714

Table 2 shows the correlation coefficients calculated from the values in Table 1.

Table 2. Correlation coefficients between R indices and chemical properties of benzenoid hydrocarbons.

Property	Van^1	Van^2	Van^3	Van^{1i}	Van^{2i}	Van^{3i}
BP	0,9539	0,9641	0,9911	0,8016	0,8513	0,9278
π -ele	0,9327	0,9453	0,9908	0,8750	0,9255	0,9771
MW	0,9450	0,9561	0,9949	0,8666	0,9110	0,9685
PO	0,9224	0,9369	0,9872	0,8804	0,9342	0,9819
MV	0,9912	0,9889	0,9837	0,7826	0,7894	0,8805
MR	0,9223	0,9368	0,9872	0,8801	0,9342	0,9820

As can be seen in Table 2, the third Van index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a boiling point of 0.9911. The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 2-4.

The linear regression equation between the third Van index and the boiling point is

$$y = -87,5578 + 17,0540x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 2.

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

Figure 2. Linear regression model of the third Van index with boiling point

The quadratic regression equation relating the third Van index to the boiling point is

$$y = -245,7036 + 29,9581x - 0,2402x^2$$

and Figure 3 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 3. Quadratic regression model of the third Van index with boiling point

The cubic regression equation relating the third Van index to the boiling point is

$$y = -246,3365 + 30,0442x - 0,2437x^2 + 5.10^{-4}x^3$$

and Figure 4 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 4. Cubic regression model of the third Van index with boiling point

As can be seen in Table 2, the third Van index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a π -electron energy of 0.9908. The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 5-7.

The linear regression equation between the third Van index and the π -electron energy is

$$y = -4,7499 + 1,0100x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Linear regression model of the third Van index with π -electron energy

The quadratic regression equation relating the third Van index to the π -electron energy is

$$y = -2,7677 + 0,8483x + 0,0030x^2$$

and Figure 6 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 6. Quadratic regression model of the third Van index with π -electron energy

The cubic regression equation relating the third Van index to the π -electron energy is

$$y = 3,7993 - 0,0443x + 0,0395x^2 - 0,0005x^3$$

and Figure 7 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 7. Cubic regression model of the third Van index with π -electron energy

As can be seen in Table 2, the third Van index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a molecular weight of 0.9949. The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 8-10.

The linear regression equation between the third Van index and the molecular weight is

$$y = -30,0206 + 8,6643x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Linear regression model of the third Van index with molecular weight

The quadratic regression equation relating the third Van index to the molecular weight is

$$y = -16,1539 + 7,5328x + 0,0211x^2$$

and Figure 9 displays the graph of this equation.

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

Figure 9. Quadratic regression model of the third Van index with molecular weight

The cubic regression equation relating the third Van index to the molecular weight is

$$y = 23,8296 + 2,0984x + 0,2432x^2 - 0,0028x^3$$

and Figure 10 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 10. Cubic regression model of the third Van index with molecular weight

As can be seen in Table 2, the third Van index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a polarization of 0.9872. The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 11-13.

The linear regression equation between the third Van index and the polarization is

$$y = -5,5958 + 1,2633x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 11.

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

Figure 11. Linear regression model of the third Van index with polarization

The quadratic regression equation relating the third Van index to the polarization is

$$y = -2,8097 + 1,0360x + 0,0042x^2$$

and Figure 12 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 12. Quadratic regression model of the third Van index with polarization

The cubic regression equation relating the third Van index to the polarization is

$$y = 5,1459 - 0,0453x + 0,0484x^2 - 0,0006x^3$$

and Figure 13 displays the graph of this equation.

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

Figure 13. Cubic regression model of the third Van index with polarization

As can be seen in Table 2, the first Van index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a molar volume of 0.9912. The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 14-16.

The linear regression equation between the first Van index and the molar volume is

$$y = -23,7048 + 3,1846x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Linear regression model of the first Van index with molar volume

The quadratic regression equation relating the first Van index to the molar volume is

$$y = -70,1447 + 29,4372x - 0,4840x^2$$

and Figure 15 displays the graph of this equation.

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

Figure 15. Quadratic regression model of the first Van index with molar volume

The cubic regression equation relating the first Van index to the molar volume is

$$y = -2,9501 + 7,2699x + 1,8492x^2 - 0,0791x^3$$

and Figure 16 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 16. Cubic regression model of the first Van index with molar volume

As can be seen in Table 2, the third Van index gave the highest correlation coefficient with a molar refractivity of 0.9872. The graphs of the linear, quadratic, and cubic regression equations of this relationship are given in Figures 17-19.

The linear regression equation between the third Van index and the molar refractivity is

$$y = -14,0658 + 3,1846x$$

and the graph of this equation is shown in Figure 17.

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

Figure 17. Linear regression model of the third Van index with molar refractivity

The quadratic regression equation relating the third Van index to the molar refractivity is

$$y = -7,2057 + 2,6249x + 0,0104x^2$$

and Figure 18 displays the graph of this equation.

Figure 18. Quadratic regression model of the third Van index with molar refractivity

The cubic regression equation relating the third Van index to the molar refractivity is

$$y = 14,8188 - 0,3686x + 0,1328x^2 - 0,0016x^3$$

and Figure 19 displays the graph of this equation.

DOI: <http://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11028810>

Figure 19. Cubic regression model of the third Van index with molar refractivity

Conclusions

This study focuses on determining the chemical relevance of the Van topological indices for predicting benzenoid hydrocarbons. Regression models are utilized to verify this, and statistical parameters are created for analysis. According to this data, the indicator is considered to have predictive potential. Curvilinear regression models are used to assess the chemical suitability of benzenoid hydrocarbons, employing linear, quadratic, and cubic equations. All models have demonstrated favorable outcomes for the statistical parameters under consideration. The third Van index is identified as the most promising predictive index for boiling point (BO), π -electron energy (π -ele), molecular weight (MW), polarizability (PO), and molar refractivity (MF) of benzenoid hydrocarbons based on the study utilizing curvilinear models. Also The first Van index is identified as the most promising predictive index for molar volume of benzenoid hydrocarbons based on the study utilizing curvilinear models. Figure 2-19 displays the findings for the linear, quadratic, and cubic models of each physicochemical feature analyzed in the study. This work may be beneficial to researchers interested in exploring topological indices for different chemical compounds and medications, particularly in the context of designing new drugs.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest

Funding Information: This research did not receive any financial support.

Author Contributions: This is a single author research

Data Availability: There is no data associated with this research

Statement of Usage of Artificial Intelligence: Artificial Intelligence is not used in this research.

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